

Microwave supported spectrophotometric determination of copper in environmental samples

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Abstract : A simple and sensitive microwave supported spectrophotometric method for the determination of copper using new reagent leucomalachite green has been developed. The proposed method is based on the reaction of copper(II) with potassium iodide in presence of hydrochloric acid to liberate iodine and the liberated iodine selectively oxidizes LMG to MG dye which shows absorption maximum at 610 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 0.016–0.176 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity and detection limit of method were found to be $3.8 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 0.00016 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 0.002 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. The method described was satisfactorily applied for the determination of copper in environmental, biological and pharmaceutical samples.

Keywords : Spectrophotometer, potassium iodide, leucomalachite green (LMG), pH meter, microwave oven (MW).

Introduction

Copper is one of the important nutrients for human as well as animals and plants that play an important role in biological system¹⁻³. The copper metal is broadly used in computers, radio sets, water pipes, electrical motors and kitchenware⁴⁻⁶. Excess copper causes nausea, vomiting, diarrhea like stomach and intestinal distress⁷. Manufacture of copper is utilized by the electrical industries because copper has exceptional electrical conductivity^{8,9}. Wilson's disease and jaundice in human being is a reason of addition of copper in human liver¹⁰.

A large number of sophisticated techniques have been proposed for determination of Cu^{II} like Atomic absorption spectroscopy, ICP-AES¹¹, flow injection catalytic photometric method¹², adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry¹³, flame atomic absorption¹⁴, X-ray fluorescence¹⁵, chromatography¹⁶, reverse phase-HPLC, derivative potentiometer stripping analysis¹⁷ including spectrophotometry^{18,19} with numerous reagent have been used for the determination of Cu^{II} . From all of the above methods, except spectropho-

tometry, most of the other techniques require expensive experimental setup and running cost. The factors such as, low cost of the instrument and almost no maintenance, have caused spectrophotometry to remain a popular and inevitable technique particularly in the laboratory of low budget. Many of the reported spectrophotometric methods are lack sensitivity, involve extraction and suffer from poor selectivity.

The aim of present investigation is to overcome the existing inadequacies and provide cost effective, sensitive and simple method for the determination of copper in environmental and pharmaceutical samples. The proposed method is based on the principle that copper(II) reacts with potassium iodide in acidic medium to liberate iodine. The iodine liberation was accelerated by the use of microwave radiation. The liberated iodine oxidizes LMG to MG dye. We successfully applied this method to determine copper(II) in environmental and pharmaceutical samples.

Material and methods :

Apparatus : A Systronics (India) spectrophotometer 166 with 1 cm matched quartz cells, Microwave

oven (India) Panasonic Model No. NN-CT353 and Systronics pH meter Model No. 331 were used.

Reagents : Analytical grade chemicals and double distilled water have been used during the experiments. **Cu^{II} solution :** The copper stock solution 1 mg/ml was prepared by dissolving 0.3929 g of copper sulphate (BDH) in double distilled water up to 100 ml volume. Working solutions were prepared daily by dilution of stock solution. **LMG solution (Sigma Aldrich, S. Germany) :** 0.025% LMG solution were prepared by dissolving 125 mg of LMG in 100 ml of water containing 1.5 ml 85% phosphoric acid, then made up to 250 ml with double distilled water. **KI solution (Merck) :** 2% aqueous solution of potassium iodide. **HCl solution (BDH, India) :** 0.5 M aqueous solution. **NaOH solution (Loba, India) :** 0.1 M aqueous solution. **Buffer solution :** Sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer solution (pH 4.5).

Procedure : An aliquot containing 0.4 to 4.4 µg of copper(II), 1 ml of 0.5 M HCl and 2 ml of 2% potassium iodide was added and content was heated in microwave oven at 500 W for 12 s for maximum liberation of iodine. To this 1 ml of 0.025% solution of LMG was added with gentle shaking for 2 min. Followed by addition of 4.5 ml of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide solution and 1 ml of acetate buffer solution of pH 4.5. The contents were heated in water bath at 40 °C for 2–3 min, cooled to room temperature and diluted to the mark with distilled water and kept for 20 min in water bath for full colour development. The formed MG dye was measured at 610 nm (maximum absorbance), at this wavelength reagent blank had negligible absorbance. The concentration of Cu^{II} content was established by reference to the calibration graph.

Colour reaction :

The following steps show proposed colour reaction (Scheme 1).

- (1) The reaction of copper(II) with potassium iodide in acidic medium liberated iodine.
- (2) Liberated iodine reacted with LMG to form MG dye.

Scheme 1. Reaction between KI-Cu^{II} system and LMG.

Results and discussion

Spectral characteristics : The Malachite green dye shows a maximum absorbance at 610 nm against reagent blank (Fig. 1) and the reaction system is represented in Scheme 1. The reagent blank showed insignificant absorbance at this wavelength. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 0.016–0.176 µg ml⁻¹ of copper(II) with good correlation coefficient

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of the dye and reagent blank : (A) concentration of copper, (B) reagent blank.

($r=0.999$) and an intercept of 0.0192 (Fig. 2). The slope of the calibration curve leads to a molar absorptivity of $3.8 \times 10^5 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Sandell's sensitivity²⁰ is found to be $0.00016 \text{ µg cm}^{-2}$.

Effect of reagent concentration : The effects of various parameters for quantitative results in experimental conditions are as follows. Under optimization conditions 2 ml of 2% KI (Fig. 3), 1 ml of 0.5 M HCl and 1 ml of 0.025% LMG (Fig. 4) were required for

Fig. 2. Calibration curve for the determination of copper.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on color reaction.

Fig. 3. Effect of KI concentration on colour reaction.

Fig. 4. Effect of the concentration of LMG.

full color development. Absorbance remains unchanged at higher concentration of reagents.

Effect of pH : The most suitable pH range was found to be 4.4 ± 0.5 for which 4.5 ml of 0.1 M NaOH was required (Fig. 5). Above pH 5.0 the solution becomes turbid and below pH 4.0 no color was observed. The colored species stabled for more than ten days under the optimum condition.

Effect of temperature and time : Liberation of iodine was not easily found by prolonged heating. Elimination of this problem is done by using microwave oven. Suitable range for heating was medium power at 12 s in a covered graduated beaker for sufficient liberation of iodine (Fig. 6). The content required heating on a water bath at 40 °C for 2–3 min. The volume was made up to 25 ml. Maximum absorbance was obtained after 20 min and the color was stable for more than ten days.

Fig. 6. Effect of time on colour reaction.

Reproducibility : The reproducibility of the method was checked by seven replicate analyses of 2 µg per 25 ml of copper solution. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0045 and 0.90% respectively.

Effect of foreign species : The effects of various foreign species which may interfere in the copper determination were studied. The method was found to be

free from most of the foreign species. Selenium interferes this can be masked by DMG ethanolic solution²¹. Interference of Fe³⁺ can be masked by sodium fluoride (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of foreign species (conc. of copper : 2 µg per 25 ml)

Foreign species	Added as	Tolerance limit (µg/ml)
Na ⁺	NaCl	2000
K ⁺	KCl	2000
CO ₃ ²⁻	Na ₂ CO ₃	2000
SO ₄ ²⁻	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	2000
Cl ⁻	NH ₄ Cl	2000
Ca ²⁺	CaCl ₂	1500
CH ₃ COO ⁻	CH ₃ COONH ₄	1200
Mg ²⁺	MgCl ₂	1000
Se ²⁺	SeO	30
Fe ³⁺	FeCl ₃	20
Cr ³⁺	Cr(NO ₃) ₃	20

The amount causing ±2% error in absorbance value.

Applications :

Determination of copper level in water : Water samples were collected from Nawapara in Raipur district and were tested for the presence of copper by the proposed method. Negligible amount of copper was found in tap water. Applicability of the method was checked by recovery test by adding known amount of copper to tap water samples. The percent recovery was found to be 98–99% (Table 2).

Determination of copper in pharmaceutical samples : A multivitamin tablet containing copper (Atoroz, certified value of copper is 0.90 mg and Supradyn, certified value of copper is 3.39 mg) was first dissolved in

Table 2. Determination of copper level in water samples from Raipur district (Chhattisgarh)

Originally found	Added (µg)	Found (µg)	Recovery (%)
(a)	(b)	(c)	c-a/b × 100
0	10	9.9 ± 0.3	99
0	20	19.9 ± 0.4	99
0	30	29.3 ± 0.3	98

Volume : 25 ml, seven replicate analyses.

aqua regia and then evaporated to dryness using sand bath. The residue was again evaporated to dryness after dissolving with water. The residue dissolved with 5 ml of dil. HCl and volume made up to 100 ml using distilled water. An aliquot of suitable diluted solution were analyzed by the proposed method for copper and also by reported method²². Iron can be removed from solution by precipitation with saturated solution of sodium fluoride. The results are as; Atoroz tablet (Khandelwal Lab. Pvt Ltd., Mumbai) contains 0.87 mg copper (reported²² 0.89 mg) and Supradyn tablet (Nicholas Piramal Ltd.) contains 3.35 mg copper (reported²² 3.34 mg) (Table 3).

Table 3. Determination of copper in pharmaceutical sample

Sample	Copper found	
	Present method	Reported method ²²
Multivitamin tablet	(mg)	(mg)
Atoroz ^a	0.87	0.89
Supradyn ^b	3.35	3.34

Certified value of copper in tablet.

^aAtoroz, Khandelwal Laboratories (P.) Ltd., Mumbai : 0.90 mg per tablet. ^bSupradyn, Nicholas Piramal Ltd., India : 3.39 mg per tablet.

Determination of copper in used oil sample from transformer : Samples (oil) collected at different times from EE (STM) I Sub transmission CSPDCL, Raipur, were tested for copper. 1 ml of this sample oil was taken in to 100 ml calibrated flask which was diluted using distilled water up to mark. 1 ml of aliquot of sample solution was used for copper determination by present method as well as by reported method²². Sample-1 contains 2.86 mg copper (reported²² 2.88 mg) and Sample-2 contains 2.87 mg copper (reported²² 2.92 mg). The samples show copper concentration equivalent to the results obtained by the reported method²² (Table 4).

Table 4. Determination of copper in oil EE (STM) I Sub transmission CSPDCL, Raipur

Sample	Copper found	
	Present method	Reported method ²²
	(mg)	(mg)
Sample-1	2.86	2.88
Sample-2	2.87	2.92

Table 5. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Reagent	(nm)	Determination range in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Remarks
Benzidithiosemicarbazide ¹⁸	380	0.5–4.0	Extraction in chloroform
Neo-cuproin ²²	457	Upto 4.0	Less sensitive, extraction in chloroform
Trimethoxy phenyl flurone ²³	552	0–0.6	Preconcentration process required
2-Acetylpyridine 4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone (APPT) ²⁴	440	0.2–5.0	Less sensitive
Leucomalachite green (proposed method)	610	0.016–0.176 μg	Simple and highly sensitive

Conclusion

This article reports the use of LMG for first time as a new reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} . The method is simple, sensitive and cost effective. The method involves no extraction steps, thereby the use of organic solvents, which are generally toxic in nature are avoided. The stability of formed MG dye is an added advantage of the method. The satisfactory applicability of the proposed procedure for the determination of Cu^{II} in environmental and pharmaceutical samples shows the utility of the method. The method is compared with other established spectrophotometric method and found superior in terms of simplicity, sensitivity, applicability for samples of different matrices etc. (Table 5).

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